

Apparent Molar Volume of some ω -Amino Acids in Aqueous Guanidine Hydrochloride Solutions at 15 and 25°

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Apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) of ω -amino acids, namely, glycine, β -alanine, γ -aminobutyric acid, δ -aminovaleric acid and ε -aminocaproic acid, have been determined in aqueous 6 *m* guanidine hydrochloride (GuCl) solutions at 15 and 25° using a vibrating-tube digital densimeter. The transfer volumes were evaluated for the amino acids studied in going from water to aqueous guanidine hydrochloride. The transfer properties are interpreted in terms of stronger interactions, a cosphere overlap model of guanidine hydrochloride molecules with the charged centres of the zwitterions (amino acid molecules) being compared to ion-nonpolar-group interactions.

Investigations on the volumetric properties of amino acids provide valuable informations which ultimately lead to a better understanding of the behaviour of biological macromolecules or proteins. In spite of the influence of heat and radiation, the chemical denaturing agents such as concentrated salt solutions also have large effects on the structure and properties of proteins¹, including solubility, denaturation and the activity of enzymes. Therefore, study of the behaviour of model compounds of proteins like amino acids are of importance. Nandi and Robinson² studied the salting-in or salting-out effects of several salts on biological macromolecules and suggested that the salts interact directly with the peptide group. Denaturation of proteins have been studied extensively in presence of urea³ and guanidine hydrochloride⁴. Guanidine hydrochloride is a strong denaturant for proteins and has been used as a sub-unit dissociating agent in complex systems⁵.

Here, the limiting apparent molar volumes of five ω -amino acids, viz. glycine (Gly), β -alanine (β -Ala), γ -aminobutyric acid (γ -Aba), δ -aminovaleric acid (δ -Amv), and ε -aminocaproic acid (ε -Ahx), in aqueous guanidine hydrochloride solutions over the concentration range 0.05–0.50 mol kg⁻¹ have been reported. The use of ω -amino acids permits individual estimations of the charged end-groups and the CH₂ group contributions which ultimately suited for the denaturation of proteins. Guanidine hydrochloride was chosen as it is reported to interact strongly, 2–3 times more effective than urea in denaturing proteins.

Results and Discussion

The apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) of amino acids in 6 *m* guanidine hydrochloride solutions were calculated using the relation,

$$V_\phi = 1000 (\rho_0 - \rho) / m \rho \rho_0 + M / \rho \quad (1)$$

where *m* is the molality, *M* the molar mass of the solute, ρ the measured density of solution and ρ_0 the density of the 6 *m* GuCl solution at a particular temperature. The V_ϕ for

amino acids in aqueous guanidine hydrochloride solutions was found to vary linearly with molality. The $V_\phi - m$ data were least-square fitted into the equation,

$$V_\phi = V_\phi^\circ + b_v m \quad (2)$$

where, V_ϕ° is the apparent molar volume at infinite dilution and b_v is an empirical constant. The values of V_ϕ° and b_v calculated using HP9000 data processing unit are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF V_ϕ° AND b_v FOR AMINO ACIDS IN 6 *m* GuCl AT 15 AND 25**

Amino acid	15°		25°	
	V_ϕ° cm ³ mol ⁻¹	b_v cm ³ kg mol ⁻²	V_ϕ° cm ³ mol ⁻¹	b_v cm ³ kg mol ⁻²
Glycine	48.72 (0.16)	-175 (0.37)	46.83 (0.11)	83 (0.28)
β -Alanine	62.78 (0.04)	-01 (0.10)	63.52 (0.24)	-206 (0.88)
γ -Aminobutyric	77.63 (0.05)	27 (0.14)	77.74 (0.09)	69 (0.03)
δ -Aminovaleric	92.84 (0.12)	48 (0.33)	93.68 (0.14)	-126 (0.77)
ε -Aminocaproic	109.25 (0.10)	44 (0.29)	109.94 (0.17)	-54 (0.79)

*Values in parentheses are standard errors:

The apparent molar volumes of amino acids are less than those of neutral molecules and approach those of ionic species of similar size, due to the fact that in water they are present as zwitterions⁶,

The volume decrease caused by the presence of the charges would be quantitatively known if the volume change of the process could be determined. In this equation R is the rest of the molecule and is not necessarily hydrocarbon-like.

The limiting apparent molar volumes of the amino ac-

ids in aqueous guanidine hydrochloride at each temperature are larger than the corresponding values in water⁷. It can also be noted that the limiting apparent molar volumes of the amino acids in aqueous guanidine hydrochloride at 25° are larger than at 15° except glycine. The V_{ϕ}° values plotted against N_{CH_2} , the number of CH_2 groups (shown in Fig. 1) in the backbone chain, yielded straight lines at 15 and 25°. The $V_{\phi}^{\circ} - N_{\text{CH}_2}$ data could, therefore, be regressed by

$$V_{\phi}^{\circ} = V_{\phi}^{\circ}(\text{NH}_3^+, \text{COO}^-) + \sum_{n=1}^{N_{\text{CH}_2}} n V_{\phi}^{\circ}(\text{CH}_2) \quad (4)$$

where, $V_{\phi}^{\circ}(\text{CH}_2)$ is the volume contribution of CH_2 group in appropriate units and $V_{\phi}^{\circ}(\text{NH}_3^+, \text{COO}^-)$ is identified as contribution due to polar end-groups $-\text{NH}_3^+$ and $-\text{COO}^-$. It was also seen that the apparent molar volume in general increases with the increasing molar mass and size of the amino acids. These results indicate that the volume contribution of the hydrocarbon portion of the amino acid is proportional to the molecular weight (similar to other organic solutes) and the volume contributions due to $^+\text{H}_3\text{NCH}_2\text{COO}^-$ is not strongly affected by the hydrocarbon groups. The trend of the limiting apparent molar volume V_{ϕ}° is found to be : Gly < β -Ala < γ -Aba < δ -Amv < ε -Ahx.

The limiting apparent molar volume of transfer $\Delta V_{\text{tr}}^{\circ}$ for the amino acids studied in going from water to aqueous guanidine hydrochloride solutions, was calculated using the relation,

$$\Delta V_{\text{tr}}^{\circ} = V_{\phi}^{\circ}(\text{aq. GuCl}) - V_{\phi}^{\circ}(\text{water}) \quad (5)$$

where the limiting apparent molar volumes for ω -amino acids in water⁷ are taken from elsewhere. The limiting apparent molar volume of transfer, $\Delta V_{\text{tr}}^{\circ}$, for all the systems studied in the present work (Table 2) are positive and it decreases with the increase in temperature except in case of δ -aminovaleric acid. It was also seen that the $\Delta V_{\text{tr}}^{\circ}$ is highest for γ -Aba at 15° and ε -Ahx at 25°. The resulting positive transfer volumes $\Delta V_{\text{tr}}^{\circ}$ for the transfer of amino acids from water to the aqueous guanidine hydrochloride can be explained by assuming a decreased electrostriction of the solvent around the charged groups on the amino acid due to strong interactions between these groups and the $(\text{H}_2\text{N})_2\text{C}=\text{NH}_2^+$ and Cl^- ions. The reduced structure-breaking tendency of $(\text{H}_2\text{N})_2\text{C}=\text{NH}_2^+$ and Cl^- ions due to their interactions with the amino acid also contributes to the positive transfer volumes. In addition to these results, Belibagli and Ayranci⁴ also supported the positive transfer volumes $\Delta V_{\text{tr}}^{\circ}$ due to the solute-cosolute-solvent interactions. The variation of $\Delta V_{\text{tr}}^{\circ}$ with the number of CH_2 groups for ω -amino

acids gives volume contributions of different groups. The intercepts give the volume contributions of the charged end or head groups (NH_3^+ , COO^-), while the slopes give the volume contribution of the methylene (CH_2) groups. The irregularity in the variation of $\Delta V_{\text{tr}}^{\circ}$ with N_{CH_2} is due to the fact that with the increase of the latter, the charge separation increases and hence the NH_3^+ and COO^- cosphere over-

TABLE 2—VALUES OF $\Delta V_{\text{tr}}^{\circ}$ OF AMINO ACIDS IN 6 *m* GuCl AT 15 AND 25°

Amino acid	$\Delta V_{\text{tr}}^{\circ}$ ($10^{-2} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	
	15°	25°
Glycine	637	363
β -Alanine	530	481
γ -Aminobutyric	638	439
δ -Aminovaleric	546	567
ε -Aminocaproic	623	574

lap decreases. This results in an increase in salt-polar group interactions. The number of electrostricted water-molecules increases as the charge separation increases⁸. The salt-polar group interactions, therefore, cause an increasingly large number of electrostricted water molecules to be relaxed to the bulk resulting in an increase in $\Delta V_{\text{tr}}^{\circ}$ with the number of CH_2 groups.

Fig. 1. Plots of V_{ϕ}° of ω -amino acids in aqueous guanidine hydrochloride against N_{CH_2} : (O) GuCl at 15° and (●) GuCl at 25°.

Experimental

All amino acids and guanidine hydrochloride were procured from Sigma. Guanidine hydrochloride and all the amino acids except δ -aminovaleric acid were used after drying at 100° for 10 h in a vacuum oven and stored in desiccator over P_2O_5 . δ -Aminovaleric acid was dried in

vacuo over P_2O_5 at 4° before use. All amino acids were of chromatographic purity. The purity of $GuCl$ was checked by comparing the absorption spectrum below 350 nm with that given by Nozaki⁹. Double-distilled water was deionised by passing it through two Cole-Parmer mixed-bed ion-exchange columns and degassed by boiling it before using for preparation of solutions. Measurements were carried out only on fresh solutions prepared by mass.

An Anton Paar DMA 60/601 densimeter with precision of $\pm 3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ was used for density measurement of the solution. The temperature in the measuring cell was controlled to $\pm 0.01^\circ$ and monitored with a Paar DT-100-20 thermometer. The densimeter was calibrated using the literature data for densities of dry air¹⁰ and pure water¹¹ at 15 and 25° . The partial molar volume of aqueous sodium chloride solution determined at 25° agreed within $\pm 0.3\%$ of the reported values¹². The partial molar volume of glycine in water also agreed within $\pm 0.02\%$ of the values reported¹³.

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